

Perceived Parenting Style and its role in Children's Sense of Self

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Abstract

Parents serve as vital protective factors for their children. They teach how to approach difficulties in life, help form worldviews, and foster the development of the children's self, and the understanding of his/her existence and self-worth. The aim of the present study was to investigate the impact of parenting styles on the sense of self of university students. For this purpose, data was collected from 131 undergraduate university students from Delhi NCR. Perceived Parenting Style Scale and the Sense of Self scale were used to evaluate the relationship between the variables. ANOVA was computed using SPSS-21. The results revealed a significant difference in a way that students who perceived their parents to be permissive exhibit a high sense of self when compared to those with authoritarian parenting style, who portray a low sense of self. However, students with authoritative parenting style show a moderate sense of self. The practical implication of the main finding can be related to parent training and educational programs, and counselling setup. That is, parents who are emotionally available and supportive to their children's needs, but who also set realistic consequences, are more likely to raise children who hold a positive view of themselves.

Keywords: parenting styles, authoritative, authoritarian, Permissive, Sense of self

Introduction

Parents build the fundamental structure that is important for the overall development of children. The parenting process is exemplified as an act of nurturing a child in the various aspects of physical, cognitive and socio-emotional development (Zahedani et al., 2016). It refers to the method by which parents engage in the process of raising their children. A consequential approach to comprehend parental influence on child development is the notion of 'parenting styles' (Baumrind, 1966). A parenting style is the representation of how parents respond to the demands of the child, the standard strategies they use in child nurturance. Parenting styles are linked to how the parent/parents themselves were born and raised, as well as their society, culture, and their exposure to different life affairs. This, in turn affects the child in an emotional, social, intellectual, and spiritual manner.

Based on the dimensions of parental demandingness (the degree to which the parents foist limits for the child's behaviour) and responsiveness (the degree to which parents show warmth, involvement), a four-fold parenting style classification has been introduced (Baumrind, 1991, Maccoby & Martin, 1983). *Authoritative* parents are high on demandingness and responsiveness, that is, they are controlling, but at the same time, not restrictive. Parental demands and expectations are clear, but feedback and opinions of the child are also solicited and valued (Crockett & Hayes, 2011). *Authoritarian* parents impose limits onto the child based on strict supervisory conditions (Badgular & Mundada, 2014). They exhibit a low level of engagement toward the child, and adult-centred control. *Permissive* parents are warm and accepting towards the needs and demands of the child and are more autonomy granting than controlling (Baumrind, 1991). A fourth parenting style was added to Baumrind's typology by Maccoby and Martin (1983), namely, neglectful parenting style. *Neglectful* parents are low on both responsiveness and demandingness. They fail to monitor the actions and behaviour of the child. An environment of non-involvement characterized by a non-controlling attitude is typical of this style of parenting.

Perceived parenting styles are described as the opinions of children about their parents' behavioural styles and strategies of responding to their needs and demands. Dixon, Graber, and Brooks-Gunn (2008) described perceived parental styles as the attitudinal and behavioural models exhibited by the parents towards the needs and demands of the child.

Effect of Parenting Styles on Child Development

Parenting style plays a vital role in child development and acts as a main influence on a child's life (Joseph & John, 2008). The four different styles of parenting are known to vary according to their impact upon the various developmental aspects of children. Furthermore, the authoritarian style of parenting detracts from academic aspects by dampening problem solving and facilitating dependence on the parent's directions. Consequently, child passivity has been directly linked to the authoritarian style of parenting, and a lack of interest in college. Also, uncontrolled environments do not foster self-regulation in children. Permissive and neglectful styles of parenting also have been directly related with academic underachievement of the child (Baumrind, 1991).

Concept of Self

An individual's relationship with their caregivers serves as the foundation for the development of their emotional, psychological, social, physical and personality development. Caregivers teach the infant how to approach difficulties in life, help form worldviews, and foster the child's development of the self, that is, the positive or negative view of one's existence and self-worth. The term 'self' has acquired varied meanings, and all of them differently answer the common question "Who am I?" (Markus & Kitayama, 1991). Various perspectives on 'self' reveal that the self of an individual is a social construct that aims to discover meaning and sense of one's actions and their purpose in life.

The concept has been researched and explored from diverse perspectives in the Indian and western context. In the Indian worldview, self has its definition in a unique perspective in comparison to the western context (Bharati, 1985). Equivalent to the notion of sense of self is *Ahamkara* in the Indian context. In the Indian tradition, the personal identity experience or sense-of-self is termed as '*Aham*' which is translated as 'I' (Tayal & Sharma, 2022). *Ahamkara* is considered the function of mind which includes the everyday thoughts and feelings of an individual about oneself. It is understood as the mechanism of 'I-maker' or the ability of mind to take on identities by relating to things as 'me' or 'mine'.

The interdependent construal of self, views the person not as segregated from the social context but as less differentiated and more associated to others. However, the essence of the Western culture is to become self-sufficient and self-reliant in terms of one's distinct attributes (Johnson, 1985). This view of the self gives rise to the proceedings/ higher order needs like self-actualization, which refers to developing one's unique potential.

Sense of Self

In exploring the independent (individualistic) and the interdependent (collectivistic) construal of self, individuals develop an understanding of themselves. Encompassing this notion ‘Sense of self’ has been defined by Flury and Ickes (2007). The basic idea is that individuals who know themselves well possess a strong self-sense and are better able to decide for themselves (self-select) particular activities they will enjoy and subsequently participate in. Individuals who exhibit a strong sense of personal identity/ sense of self have a firm awareness of who they are; they have a clear stand on their opinions that is not supposed to fluctuate by external demands, and have personal preferences (Flury & Ickes, 2007). Such individuals need not imitate the personality of another person because their own personality is well-defined. Their well-defined personality allows them to discern their own thoughts, feelings and opinions from others.

Relationship between parenting styles and sense of self

Recent research framework widely contemplates the relationship between perceived styles of parenting to numerous variables such as parent characteristics and child’s outcomes. Literature suggests that styles of child-rearing act as a determining factor in the formation of a child’s positive or negative view of the self.

Keeping in mind the above relationship, the present study aimed to investigate the role of perceived parenting style in the formation of sense of self among undergraduate university students. It was hypothesised that there would be a significant difference in sense of self among undergraduate university students with respect to their perceived parenting styles.

Method

Sample

With regard to the participants’ subject/stream of study, a majority of participants came from the arts and social science background. A relatively small percentage of participants were from the commerce, design, technology and science programs. Apart from them, only a handful of students came from the management stream. Approximately 37.4 % were in their first year of undergraduate program 24.5% were in their second year, 36.1% in their third year, and only 1.9% participants were in their fourth year of undergraduate degree. The

research study employed the convenience sampling method to collect the primary data for the study.

The present study collected data using an online questionnaire with a sample of 131 university students. To be eligible for this study, participants had to be undergraduate university students enrolled in various courses from different universities and colleges across Delhi NCR. The sample included representatives of both genders. The average age of females in this sample was 19.1 years and for men it was 19.6 years with participant ages ranging from 18-21.

Measures

Perceived Parenting Style Scale (PSS): Divya and Manikandan (2013) developed the Perceived Parenting Style Scale. The scale comprised of 30 items which evaluates the perception of children about the behaviour of their parents. It measures the participant's perception of parenting style with regard to three dimensions, namely, authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was found to be 0.79, 0.89, 0.86 for authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting style respectively. All the dimensions of the scale have an adequate level of reliability. The scale is claimed to have face validity.

The Sense of Self Scale (SOSS): Flury and Ickes (2007) developed the Sense of Self scale to evaluate the characteristics typical of those who possess a weak view of the self. It is a 12-item scale answered in a four-point Likert type scale. The test-retest reliability of this scale was found to be 0.83. The Sense of Self scale has acceptable convergent, discriminant, and predictive validity.

Procedure

For the purposes of this research, a Google Form was created and the link to the form was disseminated to the potential participants. The form consisted of 3 parts: Informed consent, Demographic details and psychological assessments used in the study. Basic information about the research study was mentioned in the form and email address of the researcher was provided in case the participants had questions regarding the study before they decide to make an informed choice. Demographic information including name, age, gender, year of

college, and email address was collected. The final section of the form had questions for both the psychological tests. There were separate instructions for each test and were mentioned prior to the starting of each test. With the help of the parenting styles inventory, the participants were classified as coming from the authoritative, authoritarian or permissive parenting style dimension. Lastly participants were thanked for their contribution and ensured that their information was kept confidential.

Data Analysis

Based on the participants' highest scores on either dimension, they were categorized into three groups for further analysis- authoritative, authoritarian and permissive parenting style groups. ANOVA was computed through the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS-21).

Results

When responses on the Perceived Parenting Style scale were analysed, 59 subjects (45.1%) reported the authoritative parenting style, 46 subjects (35.1%) reported the authoritarian style, and 26 subjects (19.8%) reported the permissive style of parenting. Thus, the subjects were divided into these three perceived parenting style groups for the remaining analysis.

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of the participants on the three parenting style groups, that is, for authoritative, authoritarian and permissive parenting. The mean score for the authoritative group (n=59) was 28.72, with a standard deviation of 3.17. The authoritarian group (n=46) had a mean of 25.45, with 5.58 as the standard deviation. The permissive group (n=26) had a mean of 35.15, with a standard deviation of 5.00.

Table 1

Mean and standard deviation of participants on the measure of perceived parenting style

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Authoritative	59	24.00	36.00	28.73	3.18
Authoritarian	46	20.00	34.00	25.46	5.59
Permissive	26	23.00	40.00	35.15	5.00

Furthermore, ANOVA was applied to assess the differences between mean scores of participants' sense of self with regard to different perceived parenting styles.

Table 2*ANOVA among the three Perceived Parenting Styles on the sense of self of participants*

Sense of Self				
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Between Groups	1744.38	2	872.19	25.74***
Within Groups	4336.98	128	33.88	
Total	6081.36	130		

***p<.001

Table 2 displays a significant difference was found in the analysis ($F=25.74$). It indicates that the authoritarian group indicated a significantly lower mean score, than the authoritative and permissive groups. Moreover, the permissive parenting style group was found to have higher sense of self than the authoritative group. The results also indicates the moderate level of sense of self amongst the authoritative parenting style group. Based on the results, the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion

The present study investigated the impact different perceived styles of parenting have on the sense of self of undergraduate university students. Parenting is an important determinant in the physical, cognitive and socio-emotional development of the child. One of the most studied approaches under parenting is the concept of parenting style. Parenting styles describe the interaction between parents and their children. They are a representation of how parents, through their attitudes and behaviours respond to the needs and demands of the child (Mayuri, Divya, & Kiran, 2017).

Parents who are part of the mesosystem, not only nurture their children physically, but their styles of nurturance contribute to the way the children understand thier existence and self-worth. All the varied definitions of 'self' answer the common question 'Who am I?'. equivalent to self in the Indian tradition is the concept of *Ahamkara*, referred to as the 'I-maker'. This function of mind includes an individual's everyday thoughts and feelings about oneself (Tayal & Sharma, 2021). The concept of *Ahamkara* enables an individual to take on a

distinct identity through associating oneself with the world around. The collectivist construal of self perceives an individual not as distinct beings, but as connected to each other. However, the Western construal of self comprehends an individual as distinct and unique in the attributes they possess. Furthermore, *ahamkara* is observed to have an influence on a wide range aspect of an individual's life namely, health (Tayal, Priya, & Sharma, 2020) life satisfaction (Gupta & Agarwal, 2021), interpersonal relationships, academic performance (Tayal & Sharma, 2022) and so on.

Although the notion of self is viewed differently in the Indian and Western construal of self, the styles of parenting in both the contexts foster the development of the child's self. This notion points to the development of a new concept, the sense of self. It is defined as an individual's perception of him/herself and an awareness of one's existence and self-worth. The concept is directly related to how one feels about oneself, the levels of self-esteem, and their confidence or lack of it thereof. Flury and Ickes (2007) differentiate between a strong and a weak sense of self. Individuals who exhibit a high sense of themselves have a firm sense of who they are, and have preferences that are individual to them. However, on the other end of the continuum, those with low sense of self are very unsure of who they are, what they think, and what their religious practices are. They have a tendency to confuse their own thoughts, feelings and perspectives with others in their social network (Flury & Ickes, 2007).

It was hypothesized that there would be a significant difference between the sense of self of the children with regard to the three different parenting styles. The results reveal that university students with permissive parenting styles have strong self of self in comparison to those with authoritarian parenting style having a low sense of self. However, the findings also suggest the moderate sense of self level of students with authoritative parenting style. The university students who discerned their parents as possessing authoritative behaviours in parenting (n=59) had a moderate level of sense of self. It suggests that individuals with authoritative parenting style do not have a very strong sense of self, however, not too weak either. Authoritative parents are responsive to their children's needs, with a high level of communication, in which the parents clearly state their demands and expectations, but the child's feedback is also valued. This finding has been supported by many theoretical frameworks on parenting styles. According to a study by Niaraki and Rahimi (2013), an individual's self-concept formation is very closely connected to parenting styles. If a child

cannot enjoy good relationship with the significant others his life, be it parents or other caregivers, the child will be negatively affected in his/her self-shaping process. This negative relationship could also be a reason that individuals with authoritative parenting styles do not have a high level of self-sense, like that of individuals with permissive parenting, where there is no interference from the parents.

An important secondary finding of this investigation was that, university students who perceived their parents as possessing the authoritarian style of parenting (n=46), indicated a low/ weak sense of self. This is because authoritarian parents are highly demanding and non-responsive. This style is permeated by a high level of psychological control over the children. Repeated failure in being able to maintain good or healthy relationships with significant others in their life can lead to self-esteem issues and a drop in one's confidence. Research suggests that authoritarian parenting style is negatively correlated with self-esteem (Bacus, 2014; Buri, 1989; Yamawaki, Peterson, & Omori, 2010).

The findings also revealed that, undergraduate university students who perceived their parents as possessing the permissive parenting style (n=26), indicated a very high level of sense of self. Permissive parents have a warm accepting and child-centred attitude, and are more autonomy granting than controlling (Baumrind, 1991). According to recent researches, the quality of responsiveness present in permissive parenting facilitates higher affirmative self-perceptions in children. Since permissive parents have no interference in the major decisions of the child, the child, over a period of time comes to view him/herself as the sole decision maker. He/she has a personal say in the career fields he opts for, as well as the attitudes and opinions he or she holds. Martinez and Garcia (2008) showed that permissive parents had children with higher self-esteem. The permissive parents often provide support and ample opportunities to the child. Because the parent allows for freedom and autonomy, the child does not have any authority figure guiding him/her into appropriate behaviour. Having a desire and being able to take a single-handed decision on any matter, the children become able to understand themselves.

Based on the findings of the present study, the following diagram (fig. 1) represents the combination of perceived parenting styles along with how high or low an individual is dependent on the self or on significant others in one's surroundings, especially parents and caregivers.

	DEPENDENCE ON SELF
DEPENDENCE ON SIGNIFICANT OTHERS	Low \longrightarrow High
High \uparrow Low	AUTHORITARIAN PARENTING
	AUTHORITATIVE PARENTING
	PERMISSIVE PARENTING

Fig 1: Permutation-Combination for the three different perceived parenting styles and self

According to the proposed combination with respect to the findings of the study, it can be said that the degree of one’s dependence either on the self or on others has a direct relation to the perceived parenting style of the individual. That is, how the person perceives his or her parental behaviour and then how they perceive their own personal identity and self-worth reflects their low, moderate or high sense of self levels. An individual whose dependence on the self is low, and high on others (parents or caregivers), reflects as being nurtured by parents who display authoritarianism. That is, when the parents are the sole decision makers for the child and the child has no say in his or her personal affairs, there is a weak understanding of oneself.

The next combination represents the participants’ balance of dependence on the self and on significant others in life. That is, the moderate dependence on oneself, as well as on significant others in the individual’s life. It means that even though the parent demarcates clear expectations to the child, at the same time, the child also has freedom to make decisions within fair boundaries. One common force acting as a precipitator to the moderate self-dependence could be divorce. Children with divorced or separated parents have a very split or dismantled family life. So, even though the single parent figure offers a fair amount freedom to the child (contributing to high self-sense), certain situational factors (divorce, for instance) could make up to the somehow low understanding of the child’s own attributes and worth.

Lastly, when an individual’s dependence on the self is high and that on others if low, the outcome represents the permissive style of parenting. That is, the child is the sole decision maker for all his/her personal and societal affairs, with a lower amount of interference on the

part of the parents. The permissive parental behaviours are non-restrictive, free from restraint and a high level of self-regulation. The parent-to-child communication in this scenario is low, but the child-to-parent communication is relatively high. Therefore, the disengagement from the side of the parents reflects directly on the strong feeling that the child has about his or her existence and self-worth. The child comes out to be concrete in his opinions, attitudes, values and decisions.

Conclusion

The influence of perceived styles of parenting on sense of self concerns practically all people, for every person forms a certain relationship with the parent figure or a significant other, and thus, an individual forms his or her perception about self. Developmental psychologists have discovered significant links between perceived styles and the overall development of children, including their perceptions about the self. According to Milu and Fathima (2015), the style of parenting children discern they receive have consequential implications on the various aspects of their development, as well as their positive and negative perceptions about themselves. Because the child receives the fundamental and rudimentary social contact and values from the parents, the importance of parenting styles should not be disregarded. Based on the findings, authoritarianism on the part of the parents leads to a weak sense of self. Permissiveness perceived parenting, on the other hand, has led to a strong sense of self. And, authoritativeness inflicted upon by the parents has led to cultivation of a moderate sense of self. The findings can be implied in parent training, educational programs, child counselling, family therapy and many other related areas. For instance, parents who are emotionally available and supportive to their children, but who also set realistic consequences for their children, are more likely to raise children who have an affirmative and healthy sense of themselves and others.

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